

FORMATION OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AS A SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019386>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01-June 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 05-June 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 09-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Psychology, linguistics,
ethnology, connections, public

ABSTRACT

Intercultural communication - communication between representatives of different human cultures. The characteristics of intercultural communication are studied at the interdisciplinary level and within such disciplines as cultural studies, psychology, linguistics, ethnology, anthropology, sociology, each of them uses its own approaches to study.

Cross-cultural communication - different different humanity culture representatives between communication (people between personal connections, less - indirect contact forms (for example, writing) and public communication). Cross-cultural of communication features interdisciplinary level and that's it such as sciences cultural studies , psychology , linguistics , ethnology , anthropology , sociology , their _ each one themselves in learning to himself special of approaches uses.

This the concept is American in the 1950s cultural an anthropologist Edward T. Hall by USA State department for America diplomats and businessmen another to countries adaptation for work came out program within included ...

Initially cross-cultural contact description for used, classic to understand culture more or less conscious and unconscious rules, standards, values, structures , works stable system - national or ethnic culture.

Cross-cultural contact scientific science as formation stage is two _ characteristic to the feature has: applies character (target different culture representatives between contact alleviation, conflict potential reduce) and interdisciplinary.

Last times processes with depends without cross-cultural contact according to studies important importance occupation is doing globalization and intensive migration.

Communication types:

1. Participants the number and they are between long relationship:

- a . interpersonal (2 people, family) - minimum number of participants, approx relationship . Of development nature this of distance narrowing or expansion.
- b . intergroup group / intragroup - distances larger , participants the number is also greater
- c . professional (in business)
- d . public (intermediary through - public information media , television)
- e . intercultural (different cultures between , previous all things own into will take)

2. Functional approach with :

- a . informative
- b . affective-evaluative (feelings , thoughts)
- c . recreational (recreation in entertainment for information)
- d . persuasive (various status people , ideological to relationships have)
- e . ceremony (various traditions , customs)

3. From the tongue use by :

- a. oral
- b. oral didn't happen

3. Oral didn't happen of communication functions

- 1. oral didn't happen speech oral the words fills
- 2. oral didn't happen contact oral to communicate opposite will come
- 3. oral didn't happen contact oral communication place clicks
- 4. oral didn't happen contact oral of speech regulator being service does _

Oral didn't happen communication :

- 1. kinesics (p expressions , views , gestures , posture)
- 2. prosody (vocal and intonation tools)
- 3. takeshika (touch)
- 4. sense (sense feeling , feelings manifestation to be)
- 5. proxemics (communication spatial structure)
- 6 chronology (contact temporary structure)

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